

Anion-tuned Layered double hydroxide (LDH) anodes for AEM water Electrolyzers: From catalyst screening to single cell performance

Malte Klingenhof,^{1‡} Philipp Hauke,^{1‡} Matthias Kroschel,¹ Xingli Wang,¹ Thomas Merzdorf,¹ Christoff Binninger,¹ Trung Ngo-Thanh,¹ Benjamin Paul,¹ Detre Teschner,^{2,3} Robert Schlögl^{2,3} and Peter Strasser^{1*}

1. Department of Chemistry, Chemical Engineering Division, Technical University Berlin, Berlin, Germany

2. Fritz Haber Institute of the Max Planck Society, Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faradayweg 4, D-14195 Berlin, Germany

3. Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion, Department of Heterogeneous Reactions, Stiftstr. 34-36, D-45470, Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany

[‡] The authors contributed equally

*Corresponding author:

Peter Strasser, email: r r r d

Abstract

Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis (AEMWE) is an attractive emerging green hydrogen technology. Yet, the scaling of trends in activity of anode catalysts for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) from a liquid-electrolyte, three-electrode environment to the two-electrode single cell format has remained poorly considered. Here, we critically investigate the scalings of kinetic and catalytic properties of a family of highly active Ni-Foam (NF) supported, anion (A^-)-tuned NiFe($-A^-$)-OER catalysts. Trends in catalytic activity suggest impressive improvements of up to 91x in three-electrode setups (3LC) compared to uncoated NF. While we demonstrate the successful qualitative structure-performance tunability into 5 cm² AEMWE single cell, we also find serious limitations in the quantitative predictability of three-electrode setups for single cell performance trends. Cell environments appear to equalize the cell performances of designer catalysts, which has important ramifications for catalyst discovery. We succeed in analyzing and discussing some of these translation limitations in terms of previously overlooked effects summarized in activity improvement factor f .

Increasing global energy demand coupled with dwindling fossil raw materials and climate change requires replacing conventional fossil fuels with sustainable ones based on renewable energy. Hydrogen, due to its high gravimetric energy storage density and versatility as reactant for industrial processes, is a favorable energy vector for future energy grids. Therefore, cost-efficient and CO₂ neutral hydrogen production is desirable.^{1,2} 96 % of the hydrogen used today is produced by steam methane reforming or coal gasification, both are greenhouse gas (GHG) intensive processes.^{3,4} Water electrolyzers that split water into H₂ and O₂ ($\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}_2 + \frac{1}{2} \text{O}_2$) using surplus energy provided by renewable energy sources (RES) represent promising near-zero emission alternatives.^{5,6}

Currently, three different low-temperature water electrolyzer technologies are in different stages of development. First, the PEMWE, the established liquid alkaline electrolyzers (AEL), and the emerging AEMWE.⁷ PEM and AEL require expensive Ir electrode materials or corrosive electrolytes (33 wt% KOH), respectively. Both appear unfavorable in the long term integration into future RES-based energy grids.⁸ AEMWE combines the advantages of both technologies. Local high pH allows for the application of non-noble, abundant and cost-efficient materials, furthermore compact stack design is suitable for dynamic linkage with fluctuating RES for production of green hydrogen.⁹ Despite broad research effort, current densities greater than 500 mA cm⁻² at reasonable potentials are still rare, especially when applying low concentrated KOH solutions.^{4,10} Most previous studies used either high concentrated KOH (1 M KOH), commercial noble metal-based catalyst or both.¹¹⁻¹³

A serious challenge for today's AEMWE catalysts R&D is the correlation and translation from liquid-electrolyte, three-electrode catalyst screening setups to realistic MEA-based two-electrode single or multi-cell electrolyzer setups. And even though there are promising laboratory scale catalysts, a reliable quantitative performance prediction to scaled-up water electrolyzers of industrial design and power has remained challenging, unconsidered and in the majority of studies unmentioned.^{9,14-18} Only few studies tackle the reasons for the performance differences between three-electrode setups and two-electrode electrolyzer cell designs are often significant for various reasons.¹⁹ This work critically contributes to the difficulties in transferring a set of new highly active catalyst from three-electrode setup to realistic single electrolyzer cells.

In the present study, we address binder-free nanostructured NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH OER catalysts prepared in-situ onto Nickel Foam (NF) substrate providing exceptionally active, synthetically scalable, structurally tunable catalyst systems. After synthesis, a controlled exchange of the 2D interlayer (-CO₃²⁻)- anions with Cl⁻ and ClO₄⁻ is applied. We show that the in-situ growth coupled to the subsequent anion tuning results in the desired chemical and structural modifications. In-situ impedance spectroscopy reveals structure-activity relations of the catalyst/support design and gives clues to their favorable performance in liquid electrolyte test. Finally, we investigate the scalability of these trends into realistic AEM water electrolyzer cells. We demonstrate the qualitative translation of

performance trends among the anode materials, yet note significant losses in relative performance gains among the deployed NiFe(-A⁻) anode catalysts. We analyze and discuss fundamental reasons for this limiting behavior.

Morphology and surface composition of tunable anion-interlaced catalysts

Powder NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH were prepared using a 30 ml autoclave and an autogenous pressure synthesis was carried out for 90 minutes at 160 °C.²⁰ Analog synthesis conditions were used to prepare LDH on NF. Precleaned NF served as substrate for the synthesis of binder-free catalyst overlayers.²¹ The prepared 3D catalyst structure will be referred to as NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF. The growth process on the NF creates a nanostructured porous electrode monolith. In a second step, the interlaced anions located in the interlayers of the 2D NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH surface were chemically exchanged into NiFe(-A⁻)-LDH@NF using a set of different anions (A⁻ = Cl⁻ and ClO₄⁻). To achieve this, the parent catalyst was exposed to excess solutions of the target anion. Herein CO₃²⁻ was exchanged with Cl⁻ followed by exchanging Cl⁻ with ClO₄⁻ resulting in the corresponding binder-free NiFe(-A⁻)-LDH@NF.

To inspect the resultant catalyst morphologies, SEM images of NF (**Figure S1 a-c**, NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF (**Figure 1a, d, g**), modified Cl⁻ and ClO₄⁻ (**Figure 1b, e, h and 1c, f, i**) suggest the successful formation of Ni(oxy)hydroxide and Fe species as well as (-A⁻) variants, though diffraction peaks of the NF background remained weak. Furthermore, the surface lamella structure evolution of the catalytically active overlayer is revealed for NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF (**Figure 1a, d, g**). The modifications via anion exchange (-A⁻) roughens the surface accompanied with an increase of the surface area. We correlate these transformations to a changing Ni/Fe ratio during the anion exchange.²² Lower magnification images (**Figure 1 a-f and Figure S1 d-f**) give an overview about the macroscopic electrode structures, indicating a homogenous coverage of NF with NiFe(-A⁻). The absence of binder allows fast mass transport at the electrode-electrolyte interface, maximizes accessible surface area and avoids I/C optimization. Also, the porous 3D structure of NF is retained after synthesis. Based on the 3D morphology of the obtained catalytic anode structures, large catalyst-electrolyte interfaces were achieved.

Figure 1: SEM, XPS and XRD investigations of NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH powder, Nickel Foam (NF) and NiFe(-A)-LDH grown on NF. a-i) SEM images of the prepared anodes, NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF (red), NiFe(-Cl)-LDH@NF (blue), NiFe(-ClO₄)-LDH@NF (green). j) Comparison of the XPS Ni 2p regions of uncoated NF (black) and NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF (red). k) Cl 2p XPS spectra of NiFe(-Cl)-LDH at NF. l) XRD investigations of powder NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH including the shifts of the (003) and (006) diffraction reflections during anion exchange and reversible structure change to NiFe(-Cl)-LDH@NF and NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH. The arrows indicate the shifts from CO₃²⁻ to ClO₄⁻ (green) and the back shift to CO₃²⁻ after aging in KOH (red).

To verify the success of our binder-free autogenous pressure synthesis, the chemical state of the catalyst surface was investigated using X-Ray Photoemission Spectroscopy (XPS). Data is reported for the catalytically active parent NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH with (**Figure 1**) and without NF support (**Figure S2**) as well as for the supported, anion-tuned NiFe(-A⁻)-LDH@NF variants (**Figure 1k** and **Figure S3**, **S4**, **S5**). Clearly, the Ni 2p spectrum of the uncoated NF and NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF differ significantly (**Figure 1j**). While both samples showed Ni(II) species, Ni(0) surface species were only present in uncoated NF. The absence of Ni(0) species in NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF confirmed the complete coating of the NF with Ni-oxide species. The Ni 2p spectra of NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF corresponded to the XPS spectra of NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH powder and reveals oxyhydroxide characteristics of the surface species, which was also confirmed for NiFe(-A⁻)-LDH@NF (**Figure S4b**,

S5b). Fe 2p core level signals (**Figure S3c**) further confirmed the in-situ growth of NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH at NF. Weak Fe 2p signals resulted from the overall very low Fe/Ni ratio.

Finally, Cl 2p spectra of NiFe(-A⁻)-LDH@NF confirm the chloride exchange (**Figure 1k, S5f**). Ni 2p and Fe 2p signal intensity declined after (-A⁻)-modification. The O 1s region showed a slight shoulder, arising from decreasing NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH layer thickness, revealing the underlying oxidic NF. XRD diffraction patterns of NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH and NiFe(-ClO₄⁻)-LDH depicted in **Figure 1l** show anion intercalation accompanied with increasing interlayer distances and the transformation from NiFe(-ClO₄⁻)-LDH back to NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH after aging.

Detailed synthesis-performance relations studying influences of preparation parameters on the catalytic reactivity are shown in **Figures S6-S11** and discussed in the Supplementary Discussion 1.

Structure-composition-catalytic OER reactivity relations

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and modeling (**Figure 2** and **Figure S12**) was applied evaluating the *faradaic capacitance* and calculating the real electroactive surface area (ECSA) of the anodes.^{23,24} The recently proposed and proven EIS-based faradaic capacitance model took the presence of uncoated NiOx layers of the NF, as well as that of non-conductive oxyhydroxide layers of anion-tuned NiFe(-A⁻)-LDH grown on NF into account.²⁴ **Figure S12** illustrates the electrical equivalent circuit (EEC) and analysis, which is described in SI.²³

Figure 2: Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) investigations determining the ECSA of the prepared NiFe(-A)-LDH@NF and NF in a three-electrode setup (3LC) and electrocatalytic OER reactivity and stability of uncoated NF, compared to NiFe(-A)-LDH@NF anodes.

LDH@NF and d) NiFe(-ClO₄)-LDH@NF recorded at 1.53 V, 1.58 and 1.63 V vs RHE. e) Calculated ECSA of uncoated NF (black) and the prepared anodes, NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF (red), NiFe(-Cl)-LDH@NF (blue) and NiFe(-ClO₄)-LDH@NF (green). f) iR-corrected linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) g) ECSA- and iR-corrected LSVs of uncoated NF (black), NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF (red), NiFe(-Cl)-LDH@NF (blue) and NiFe(-ClO₄)-LDH@NF (green). Stability investigations of h) uncoated NF, i) NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF, j) NiFe(-Cl)-LDH@NF and k) NiFe(-ClO₄)-LDH@NF anodes. The measurements were conducted in 0.1 M KOH at RT using three-electrode setup.

The Nyquist spectra of NiFe(-A⁻)-anodes exhibit two arcs. The low frequency resistance (LFR) arc proves electrode potential-dependency, the high frequency (HFR), in contrast, is potential-independent (**Figure 2 a-d**). R_{Ω} depends on the three-electrode liquid electrolyte setup (3LC) and is used for iR-correction of the depicted LSVs and CVs (**Figure 2e** and **Figure S12b**). While both semi-circles of NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF are well separated, the arcs associated with NiFe(-ClO₄)-LDH@NF and NiFe(-Cl)-LDH@NF partially merge. LFR and HFR of uncoated NF overlap. The potential dependence of the LFR confirmed its interfacial charge transfer character, R_{CT} . At +1.53 V_{RHE}, R_{CT} was dominant, yet dropped sharply at +1.58 V_{RHE} and +1.63 V_{RHE} (**Figure 2a-d** and **Figure S12 c**). High voltages increase the rate of redox reaction, thus decreasing the R_{CT} .²⁵ Still, the uncoated NF continued to suffer from large R_{CT} , more than an order of magnitude larger than for the NiFe(-A⁻)-LDH@NF anodes. NiFe(-Cl)-LDH@NF exhibited the smallest R_{CT} confirming measured trends (**Figure 2 c**). HFR remained independent of applied anode potentials for all materials suggesting specific bulk and surface characteristics of the anodes. The impedance characteristics of NiFe(-A⁻)-LDH@NF point to non-conductive coating layers, where the HFR can be used evaluating faradaic pseudo-capacitance of the electrode and, from that, its real electrochemical surface area (ECSA).^{23,24,26} When correlated with R_{CT} , deeper insights into the origins of the reported trends are possible. ECSAs plotted in **Figure 2e** has the smallest ECSA for uncoated NF, while NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF and NiFe(-Cl)-LDH@NF exhibit the largest ECSA, with NiFe(-ClO₄)-LDH@NF being in-between over the entire potential range. ECSA values of NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF and NiFe(-Cl)-LDH@NF declined with anodic potentials, resulting from oxygen bubble blocking of fractions of the surface. Our impedance analysis agrees with the trends in SEM surface morphology, where NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF showed a roughening of the electrolyte-electrode-interface. Despite comparable ECSA, NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF is less active for OER than NiFe(-Cl)-LDH@NF (**Figure 2 f, g**). Replacing Cl⁻ with ClO₄⁻ decreases the ECSA leading to declining electrocatalytic performance. Since the compositional data (Table S2) and the relatively flat (plateau-like) relation between Fe mol% and OER activity^{27,28} in the Fe mol% range of interest we conclude that there is no significant dependence of the LDH OER reactivity on the Fe mol% of the anodes. Therefore, replacing CO₃²⁻ with A⁻, effectively modulates the reactivity of the active surface sites by a targeted modulation of the interlayer chemistry. The interlayer chemistry, that is the nature of the intercalation ions and their coulomb interaction with water and the adjacent “Brucite”-type sheets controls the transition of from the non-catalytic α -phase to the catalytically active γ -LDH phase. The tuning of the interlayer chemistry by halogenate ions results in a larger molar ratio of the catalytically more active γ -LDH phase compared

to α -phase, potentially supported by varied crystallite size (larger with Cl^- , smaller with ClO_4^-).²⁹⁻³² The following section and **Figure 2 f-k** correlates the OER activities and the EIS data measured in 3LC.

The recorded OER currents of the prepared anodes were compared to uncoated NF. A three-electrode liquid electrolyte setup was applied. **Figure 2 f-g** depicts LSV and **Figure 2 h-k** CV stability measurements (**Figure S13**, discussed in SI discussion II). The LSV trends (**Figure 2 f**) reflect the improved performance of the anion tuned $\text{NiFe}(-\text{CO}_3^{2-})$ -LDH coating (red) compared to the uncoated NF (black). Subsequent adjustment of the interlayer chemistry of $\text{NiFe}(-\text{CO}_3^{2-})$ -LDH@NF using Cl^- (blue) and ClO_4^- (green) impacted the catalysis (**Figure 2 f, g**). Cl^- improved the OER activity, while ClO_4^- decreased it and is therefore not further part of the discussion. The anodic shift of the Ni redox wave further confirms formation of NiFe -LDH at the surface of the NF.³³ With the ECSA values, we evaluated the intrinsic, ECSA-normalized OER LSVs (**Figure 2 g**) confirming the correlation between ECSA and OER activity. Thus, ECSA can be used to explain the drastically increased OER activities in the three-electrode setup applying $\text{NiFe}(-\text{A}^-)$ -LDH coating to uncoated NF. Closer inspection of the voltammetric profiles in **Figure 2 f** and **g** revealed that $\text{NiFe}(-\text{CO}_3^{2-})$ -LDH@NF exhibited a defined redox wave at +1.4 V_{RHE} associated with the oxidation of Ni^{2+} to higher oxidation states ($\text{Ni}^{3+/4+}$). We directly tracked this catalyst redox process by *operando* optical analysis (change from metallic grey (Ni^{2+}) to black ($\text{Ni}^{3+/4+}$) in **Figure S14**). Uncoated NF remained metallic grey. In order to exclude the influence of Ni and Fe leaching on the catalytic activity, we performed ICP-OES of the electrolyte before and after stability measurement with the most active catalyst $\text{NiFe}(-\text{Cl}^-)$ -LDH@NF (**Table S3**). We detected a negligible amount of Ni (2.5 μg) and Fe (1.5 μg) from which we deduce a small influence on the catalytic activity.

Translating RDE to AEM Water Electrolyzer Cell performance

Overall goal of this study, like many other current studies, was tuning and enhancing the performance of the scaled-up device of the AEMWE guided by the performance gains observed in three-electrode screenings. To check whether $\text{NiFe}(-\text{A}^-)$ -LDH@NF anodes OER performance is actually transferable into practically relevant AEMWE anode environments, we first conducted measurements for the three-electrode setup at 60 °C (**Figure S15**) for a more realistic comparison. Then identical $\text{NiFe}(-\text{A}^-)$ -LDH coatings grown on NF were employed as 5 cm^2 anodes in single AEM electrolyzer cells (AEM Cell). The electrolyzer cell setup is provided in **Figure S16** and an evaluation of different cathodic PTLs, temperatures, pH, membranes and Pt cathode loadings are presented in **Figure S17**. The AEMWE polarization curves are shown in **Figure 3a**. It is very important for the discussion, that the prepared anodes do not contain liquid solubilized binder or ionomer-based catalyst inks or catalyst layers. This means that the analysis and discussion of the translation of three-electrode to cell performances, is in large contrast to MEA and other catalyst-coated-membrane design, completely exclude the consideration of catalyst ink parameters such as ionomer/catalyst ratios, catalyst loadings, film

porosity characteristics and other catalyst layer-related parameters impacting performance. ECSA and roughness factors of the cell anodes are identical to those in three-electrode since synthesis parameters were kept constant. Thus, a comparative analysis of how catalyst screening translates into cell performance is straight forward and can be reduced to fewer control parameters.

Table 1: Summarizing and comparing the 3LC with the AEM cell at 60°C.

Parameter	3LC _{60°C}	AEM Cell _{60°C}
Electrolyte (pH)	KOH (13)	KOH (13)
T	60°C	60°C
Electrode Area	1 cm ²	5 cm ²
Cathode	Pt-Mesh	Pt/C
Reference Electrode	RHE	-
Potential	1.52 V	1.52 V
Best Performance	NiFe(-Cl ⁻)-LDH@NF	NiFe(-Cl ⁻)-LDH@NF
Current Density	54 mA/cm ²	587 mA/cm ²
f	91.9x	1.9x

Figure 3: Activity tests and trends of NiFe(-A)-LDH@NF and uncoated NF measured in AEMWE single cell. (a) Comparison of the polarization curves of NiFe(-A)-LDH@NF CO₃²⁻ (red) and Cl⁻ (blue) with uncoated NF (black), dashed lines denote as iR-corrected polarization curves. (b) comparative activity improvement factors $f = \frac{j_{geom,cat\ at\ 1.52V}}{j_{geom,NF\ at\ 1.52V}}$ of anion tuning in three-electrode liquid cell (3LC) at 25°C, 60°C, AEMWE single cell (AEM Cell) and blowup (same y-axis labeling but different scale) of the AEM cell. Data for the AEM cell are iR- and HER corrected (Figure S 18c). f was calculated at the highest possible iR-corrected potential ($E_{iR}=1.52 V_{RHE}$) measured in 3LC at 60°C (Figure S15).

The cell polarization curves in **Figure 3a** qualitatively reproduce the three-electrode activity trends: The NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF anode showed superior electrocatalytic activities compared to uncoated NF, NiFe(-Cl⁻)-LDH@NF offered some additional performance benefits over NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF. Thus, our data demonstrates that the structural and compositional tuning of uncoated NF with LDH-catalyst, is principally scalable to single AEMWE cell level. We note, however, that two-electrode electrolyzer cell tests did not yield the same quantitative improvement factors as those found

in three-electrode screenings, this is summarized in **Figure 3 b** and **Table 1**. The membrane cell environment appeared to equalize the LDH-catalysts, while significantly raising uncoated NF performance. More specifically, we found that polarization curves of uncoated NF anodes trail NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF anodes by only about 20%, iR-corrected polarization curves by about 40% and iR- and HER-overpotential corrected by 80% in OER current density despite the sharply lower ECSA of uncoated NF. Calculation of the HER-overpotential is explained in SI (**Figure S18**). Thus, despite identical ECSA of the applied anodes, it was not possible to translate the 91x anode performance gain measured in three-electrode setup to the single cell AEMWE design. The uncoated NF performed much better than predicted. Furthermore, the calculated f depicted in **Figure 3 b** and **Figure S19a** and **b** clearly show the iR- and HER-contribution to the overall performance discrepancy between three-electrode and AEMWE single cell activity, which is only 60%.

To further understand the serious performance discrepancies between three-electrodes and electrolyzer cells in more detail, we re-investigated the cell anode environments including impedance, electrocatalytic behavior and chemical states before and after electrolysis. We uncovered component limitations of commercial alkaline electrolyzer setups that compromise quantitative translations of OER anode catalyst performances.

In particular, Fe 2p core level photoemission of the initially Fe-free NF (**Figure S20**) demonstrates the presence of Iron and NiOOH species at the surface cell testing (**Figure S21**). The well-documented catalytic activation of Nickel OER catalysts by atomic Fe deposition³³⁻³⁶ accompanied with anodic shift of the Ni redox wave fully accounts for the increased OER-activity of the uncoated NF and is further reported with three-electrode measurements of the NF after AEMWE single cell testing in SI (**Figure S22**). This partly explains the much smaller OER activity differences between NF and NiFe(-A⁻)-LDH@NF anodes in the AEMWE cell tests. As the level of Fe impurities in the alkaline electrolyte was identical in three-electrode screening and electrolyzer cells (same commercial alkaline reagent used), we conclude that, Fe impurities must originate from Fe corrosion of stainless-steel electrolyzer components. We use EIS under OER conditions comparing NF with the NiFe(-A⁻)-LDH@NF anodes, all performed in the AEMWE cell. Exemplary Nyquist-Plots and EEC applied for the fitting are depicted in **Figure S23 a** and **c**. As expected from our three-electrode screenings, NiFe(-CO₃²⁻)-LDH@NF showed lower R_{CT} (enhanced intrinsic OER activity) but increased R_{Ω} resulting from the catalytic active LDH overlayer (**Figure S23 b** and Supplementary Discussion II). Impedance data of the electrolyzer cell agrees well with the iR-corrected polarization curves of **Figure 3 a**. Furthermore, the R_{CT} and EIS-based ECSA of NF after AEMWE single cell testing measured in three-electrode setup reveal decreased R_{CT} but only insignificant increased ECSA of the uncoated NF. This is why, in order to account for the equalization of the performance of the anodes, we further propose OH⁻ transport between cathode, membrane and anode as bottleneck for translating catalyst three-electrode activity trends accurately into AEMWE. We recall that optimal PEMWE performance

requires perfect chemical and electrical contact accompanied with ideal ionic and electronic pathways providing optimized catalyst utilization.³⁷ As OH⁻ ions migrate from cathode to anode to replenish the local loss of OH⁻ and thereby regulate the local anode pH, only the anode surface closest to the solid membrane has the strongest impact on OER. The large ECSA, previously determined as controlling in the liquid electrolyte, three-electrode structure, turns out not decisive here, since the majority of the rough nanostructured anode surface is not in direct contact with the membrane. In other words, only a small fraction of the high ECSA designer anodes is actually involved in a high pH OER catalysts. Both mechanisms, the Iron species incorporation as well as the OH⁻ limited local OER catalysts can account for the incomplete translation of anode performance from screening to electrolyzer cell. Considering the identical liquid electrolytes (0.1 M KOH) in three-electrode setup and AEMWE single cells, we are inclined to identify low, high local pH as major reason for limited performance gains of NiFe(-A⁻)-LDH@NF anodes over NF, despite their still significantly larger ECSA.

This study critically analyzes scaling behavior between three-electrode and single AEMWE testing. A binder-free catalyst layer formed enables the comparison, since typical catalyst ink and layer parameters are absent. Combining NiFe-species with NF resulted in 91x electrocatalytically OER increase in three-electrode setup compared to uncoated NF. Impedance spectroscopy unraveled ECSA originating for favorable increased OER of NiFe(-A⁻)-anodes. NF and NiFe(-A⁻)-LDH@NF anodes kept order of the OER activity when applied to AEMWE single-cell-level. Despite identical ECSAs of the applied anodes, the same quantitative improvement was not found for two-electrode setup as described for three-electrode screenings. Strong improvement of NF is achieved via Fe incorporation and local pH conditions. Solid electrolyte setups only offer an improvement of 1.9x iR- and HER-corrected. Large ECSA, previously origin for OER activity in the three-electrode setup was not a control parameter, because for cell performance presumably contact shortcomings between rough nanostructured anode surface and membrane limit catalyst utilization.

Our study confirms the importance and usefulness of three-electrode catalyst screenings and development efforts for AEMWEs. However, at the same time, unveils limitations associated with the quantitative prediction and translation of screening performance results into AEMWE single cell or even multi cell setups.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

T r r r r A P
O

A d r r r r d r
r r r r r d d d AEM E
dd d r d d

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

P r r r r r r d

Author Contributions

M d P r d

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Financial support by the German Research Foundation (DFG) through Grant Reference Number STR 596/12-1, the federal ministry for education, research and development (Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung, BMBF) under Grant numbers 03SF0613D and 03SF0611A in the collaborative research projects „AEMready“ and „H₂-Meer“ and the federal ministry for economic affairs and energy (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie, BMWi) under Grant Number 03EIV041F in the collaborative research project “MethQuest” in the group “MethFuel” and funding by European Union’s HORIZON.3.1 - The European Innovation Council (EIC) Programme through the grant agreement 101071111 ANEMEL are gratefully acknowledged. We would like to thank the company Rubröder for their careful support in commissioning the automated spraying station (ExactaCoat OP3) used.

References

- 1 Ramachandran, R. & Menon, R. K. An Overview of Industrial Uses of Hydrogen. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* **23**, 593-598 (1998).
- 2 Ball, M. & Wietschel, M. The future of hydrogen - opportunities and challenges☆. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* **34**, 615-627, doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2008.11.014 (2009).
- 3 Kakoulaki, G. *et al.* Green hydrogen in Europe – A regional assessment: Substituting existing production with electrolysis powered by renewables. *Energy Conversion and Management* **228**, 113649, doi:10.1016/j.enconman.2020.113649 (2021).
- 4 Kou, T., Wang, S. & Li, Y. Perspective on High-Rate Alkaline Water Splitting. *ACS Materials Letters* **3**, 224-234, doi:10.1021/acsmaterialslett.0c00536 (2021).
- 5 Noussan, M., Raimondi, P. P., Scita, R. & Hafner, M. The Role of Green and Blue Hydrogen in the Energy Transition—A Technological and Geopolitical Perspective. *Sustainability* **13**, 298, doi:10.3390/su13010298 (2020).
- 6 Burton, N. A., Padilla, R. V., Rose, A. & Habibullah, H. Increasing the efficiency of hydrogen production from solar powered water electrolysis. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* **135**, 110255, doi:10.1016/j.rser.2020.110255 (2021).
- 7 Schalenbach, M. A Perspective on Low-Temperature Water Electrolysis – Challenges in Alkaline and Acidic Technology. *International Journal of Electrochemical Science*, 1173-1226, doi:10.20964/2018.02.26 (2018).
- 8 Latsuzbaia, R. *et al.* Continuous electrochemical oxidation of biomass derived 5-(hydroxymethyl)furfural into 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid. *Journal of Applied Electrochemistry* **48**, 611-626, doi:10.1007/s10800-018-1157-7 (2018).
- 9 Mukerjee, S., Yan, Y. & Xu, H. Hydrogen at Scale Using Low-Temperature Anion Exchange Membrane Electrolyzers. *Electrochem. Soc. Interface* **30**, 73 (2021).
- 10 Henkensmeier, D. *et al.* Overview: State-of-the Art Commercial Membranes for Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolysis. *J. of Echem. Energy Conversion and Storage* **18**, 024001, doi:10.1115/1.4047963] (2020).
- 11 Fortin, P. *et al.* High-performance alkaline water electrolysis using Aemion™ anion exchange membranes. *Journal of Power Sources* **451**, 227814, doi:10.1016/j.jpowsour.2020.227814 (2020).
- 12 Pushkareva, I. V., Pushkarev, A. S., Grigoriev, S. A., Modisha, P. & Bessarabov, D. G. Comparative study of anion exchange membranes for low-cost water electrolysis. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* **45**, 26070-26079, doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.11.011 (2020).
- 13 Motealleh, B. *et al.* Next-generation anion exchange membrane water electrolyzers operating for commercially relevant lifetimes. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* **46**, 3379-3386, doi:10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.10.244 (2021).
- 14 Zhu, Y. *et al.* A Perovskite Nanorod as Bifunctional Electrocatalyst for Overall Water Splitting. *Advanced Energy Materials* **7**, doi:10.1002/aenm.201602122 (2017).
- 15 Zhao, J. W., Shi, Z. X., Li, C. F., Gu, L. F. & Li, G. R. Boosting the electrocatalytic performance of NiFe layered double hydroxides for the oxygen evolution reaction

- by exposing the highly active edge plane (012). *Chem Sci* **12**, 650-659, doi:10.1039/d0sc04196c (2020).
- 16 Zhang, L. *et al.* Selenic Acid Etching Assisted Vacancy Engineering for Designing Highly Active Electrocatalysts toward the Oxygen Evolution Reaction. *Adv Mater* **33**, e2007523, doi:10.1002/adma.202007523 (2021).
- 17 Wu, C. *et al.* Iron-based binary metal-organic framework nanorods as an efficient catalyst for the oxygen evolution reaction. *Chinese Journal of Catalysis* **42**, 637-647, doi:10.1016/s1872-2067(20)63686-5 (2021).
- 18 Gorlin, M. *et al.* Tracking Catalyst Redox States and Reaction Dynamics in Ni-Fe Oxyhydroxide Oxygen Evolution Reaction Electrocatalysts: The Role of Catalyst Support and Electrolyte pH. *J Am Chem Soc* **139**, 2070-2082, doi:10.1021/jacs.6b12250 (2017).
- 19 Xu, D. *et al.* Earth-Abundant Oxygen Electrocatalysts for Alkaline Anion-Exchange-Membrane Water Electrolysis: Effects of Catalyst Conductivity and Comparison with Performance in Three-Electrode Cells. *ACS Catalysis* **9**, 7-15, doi:10.1021/acscatal.8b04001 (2018).
- 20 Klingenhof, M. *et al.* Modular Design of Highly Active Unitized Reversible Fuel Cell Electrocatalysts. *ACS Energy Letters* **6**, 177-183, doi:10.1021/acseenergylett.0c02203 (2020).
- 21 Dresp, S. *et al.* An efficient bifunctional two-component catalyst for oxygen reduction and oxygen evolution in reversible fuel cells, electrolyzers and rechargeable air electrodes. *Energy & Environmental Science* **9**, 2020-2024, doi:10.1039/c6ee01046f (2016).
- 22 Klingenhof, M. *et al.* Modular Design of Highly Active Unitized Reversible Fuel Cell Electrocatalysts. *ACS Energy Letters* **6**, 177-183, doi:10.1021/acseenergylett.0c02203 (2021).
- 23 Watzele, S. & Bandarenka, A. S. Quick Determination of Electroactive Surface Area of Some Oxide Electrode Materials. *Electroanalysis* **28**, 2394-2399, doi:10.1002/elan.201600178 (2016).
- 24 Dionigi, F. *et al.* Intrinsic Electrocatalytic Activity for Oxygen Evolution of Crystalline 3d-Transition Metal Layered Double Hydroxides. *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl* **60**, 14446-14457, doi:10.1002/anie.202100631 (2021).
- 25 Vincent, I., Lee, E. C. & Kim, H. M. Comprehensive impedance investigation of low-cost anion exchange membrane electrolysis for large-scale hydrogen production. *Sci Rep* **11**, 293, doi:10.1038/s41598-020-80683-6 (2021).
- 26 Watzele, S. *et al.* Determination of Electroactive Surface Area of Ni-, Co-, Fe-, and Ir-Based Oxide Electrocatalysts. *ACS Catalysis* **9**, 9222-9230, doi:10.1021/acscatal.9b02006 (2019).
- 27 Görlin, M. *et al.* Oxygen Evolution Reaction Dynamics, Faradaic Charge Efficiency, and the Active Metal Redox States of Ni-Fe Oxide Water Splitting Electrocatalysts. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **138**, 5603-5614, doi:10.1021/jacs.6b00332 (2016).
- 28 Louie, M. W. & Bell, A. T. An Investigation of Thin-Film Ni-Fe Oxide Catalysts for the Electrochemical Evolution of Oxygen. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **135**, 12329-12337, doi:10.1021/ja405351s (2013).

- 29 Dresp, S. *et al.* Molecular Understanding of the Impact of Saline Contaminants and Alkaline pH on NiFe Layered Double Hydroxide Oxygen Evolution Catalysts. *ACS Catal.*, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscatal.1021c00773> (2021).
- 30 Hauke, P., Klingenhof, M., Wang, X., de Araújo, J. F. & Strasser, P. Efficient electrolysis of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural to the biopolymer-precursor furandicarboxylic acid in a zero-gap MEA-type electrolyzer. *Cell Reports Physical Science* **2**, 100650, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xcrp.2021.100650> (2021).
- 31 Dionigi, F. *et al.* In-situ structure and catalytic mechanism of NiFe and CoFe layered double hydroxides during oxygen evolution. *Nature Communications* **11**, doi:10.1038/s41467-020-16237-1 (2020).
- 32 Dionigi, F. *et al.* Intrinsic Electrocatalytic Activity for Oxygen Evolution of Crystalline 3d-Transition Metal Layered Double Hydroxides. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* **n/a**, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202100631> (2021).
- 33 Deng, J. *et al.* Morphology Dynamics of Single-Layered Ni(OH)₂/NiOOH Nanosheets and Subsequent Fe Incorporation Studied by in Situ Electrochemical Atomic Force Microscopy. *Nano Lett* **17**, 6922-6926, doi:10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b03313 (2017).
- 34 Klaus, S., Cai, Y., Louie, M. W., Trotochaud, L. & Bell, A. T. Effects of Fe Electrolyte Impurities on Ni(OH)₂/NiOOH Structure and Oxygen Evolution Activity. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **119**, 7243-7254, doi:10.1021/acs.jpcc.5b00105 (2015).
- 35 Son, Y. J. *et al.* Anodized Nickel Foam for Oxygen Evolution Reaction in Fe-Free and Unpurified Alkaline Electrolytes at High Current Densities. *ACS Nano*, doi:10.1021/acsnano.0c10788 (2021).
- 36 Trotochaud, L., Young, S. L., Ranney, J. K. & Boettcher, S. W. Nickel-iron oxyhydroxide oxygen-evolution electrocatalysts: the role of intentional and incidental iron incorporation. *J Am Chem Soc* **136**, 6744-6753, doi:10.1021/ja502379c (2014).
- 37 Hegge, F. *et al.* Efficient and Stable Low Iridium Loaded Anodes for PEM Water Electrolysis Made Possible by Nanofiber Interlayers. *ACS Applied Energy Materials* **3**, 8276-8284, doi:10.1021/acsaem.0c00735 (2020).

TOC: For table of contents only

